

DEVELOPMENT OF ORAL RUSSIAN SPEECH AS A FACTOR IN THE FORMATION OF PERSONALITY AND PROFESSIONAL SKILLS OF UZBEK YOUTH

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Abstract: The article analyzes the issues of studying the Russian language and developing oral speech among Uzbek youth. The role of the Russian language in the historical context and modern life of Uzbekistan is considered. The social status and difficulties that complicate the use of language for self-expression in everyday communication, in social networks, on forums and other platforms are noted. The reasons for the negative impact of gadgets on the formation of Russian speech are highlighted. As recommendations, it is proposed to pay more attention to reading fiction and scientific literature, as well as the active development of oral communication.

Keywords: Russian language, youth, social status, education, communication and culture, migration, filler words, diction, gadgets, transliteration, professional development

Introduction

The Russian language as a means of communication among the people and nationalities living in Uzbekistan, as well as one of the world-recognized languages of science, education and the Internet, plays a vital role in the cultural, economic and scientific development of our country.

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan stipulates that the Russian language is the language for interethnic communication [1].

Historical facts show that this language played an important role in the history of Uzbekistan, especially during the period when it was part of the former USSR. In those years, the Russian language was widely used in the spheres of production, education, science, culture, trade, everyday life and others. In multinational Uzbekistan, the Russian language served as a means of communication between representatives of different peoples and nations. After the collapse of the USSR, the Russian language retained its role in business relations, diplomacy and education.

Methods

Today, the Russian language remains in demand not only among the old but also the young generations of Uzbekistan. In order to support the economic development of our country, both English and Russian languages are actively promoted among young people.

The Russian language still maintains a high social status:

In the field of education, especially when obtaining higher education in technical and medical specialties. Many universities offer educational programs in Russian, and knowledge of it significantly expands employment opportunities, including in international companies in the field of communication and culture. In large cities such as Tashkent, Samarkand and Bukhara, Russian is actively used in everyday communication. This is due to the development of tourism. Young people consume Russian-language content - films, books, social networks, and also follow Russian bloggers and musicians. In the field of migration. Many young compatriots are considering the possibility of working or studying in Russia, and knowledge of this

language facilitates labor migration. Labor migration has shown that if a person who speaks Russian came to Russia to earn money, he was in more favorable conditions. Even from the point of view that it is not so easy to deceive him, since a person can read the laws [1].

The development of oral Russian speech among young people plays an important role in the formation of their personality and professional skills. The ability to clearly and competently express your thoughts contributes to effective communication and increases confidence in various life situations. However, despite the importance of this skill, difficulties in mastering the Russian language are increasingly emerging, such as:

a) limited vocabulary. Decreased interest in reading fiction, the replacement of live communication with text messages and memes, as well as fascination with the virtual environment led to the impoverishment of speech. It is becoming increasingly difficult for young people to clearly and fully express their thoughts;

b) the use of filler words. Frequent use of interjections such as "uh", "well", "as if", "like", "in short" and others disrupts the logic of statements, makes it difficult for listeners to perceive speech and creates the impression of uncertainty. These filler words have become so deeply embedded in oral speech that they are often used even in their native Uzbek language. c) unclear diction and monotony of speech. Insufficient articulation of sounds and monotonous intonation make speech unexpressive. This may be due to the phonetic peculiarities of the native language, as well as the influence of English-speaking culture, including through music and social networks.

d) fear of public speaking. Anxiety in front of an audience, fear of making a mistake or being misunderstood cause stiffness, pauses and incoherence of speech, interfering with the clear presentation of thoughts;

d) difficulties in formulating thoughts in a foreign language. Lack of oral speech practice makes it difficult to consistently present ideas, especially in stressful or official situations;

e) ignorance of the norms of the literary Russian language. The inability to distinguish between styles (colloquial and formal-business) can cause difficulties in professional communication and reduce the level of speech culture

Discussion

Today, young people are trying to learn more foreign languages: for some, it is just an interest, for others, it is an increase in their professional potential, for others, it is self-affirmation. All conditions have been created for learning a foreign language, including Russian: from training courses to tutoring, from audio materials to e-books, from educational technical equipment to specialized educational institutions. The main thing that young people need is diligence, hard work and desire. They can independently learn any foreign language. All the conditions created by modern pedagogy, technology and the state serve this purpose.

According to young people, gadgets are of great importance as the main assistants in learning the Russian language.

The widespread use of electronic resources and equipment creates an opportunity for independent development of the language learner. But, to do this, the language learner must first determine what foreign language he needs, how important the language is for his professional development and what his own desires are, and then set a clear goal. Only in this case, any techniques, methods and gadgets will bring him real benefit in learning the language. It must be admitted that with the development of civilization in the educational process, the need for various gadgets increases. The use of gadgets makes learning a language more exciting and effective: smartphones, tablets and laptops allow you to listen to podcasts, watch videos, use dictionaries and simulators at any time. But, in the educational process, if we rely only on modern gadgets, we will not achieve good results in learning the language. As a result, the oral speech of students lags behind in development. Gadgets, although they have a number of useful functions, can make it difficult to learn Russian as a foreign language for a number of reasons:

firstly, when learning a foreign language, including Russian, young people often prefer short videos, images and memes with minimal text and speech load, which reduces interest in reading and writing in Russian;

secondly, a simplified language is widely used in social networks, which is a mixture of Russian, Uzbek and English,

as well as the use of transliteration - a way of writing words of one language (most often Russian) using the letters of another alphabet, most often Latin. Such communication complicates the development of correct written and oral speech;

thirdly, dependence on autocorrection and online translators reduces the need to memorize grammar rules, spelling and vocabulary of the Russian language, etc.

Results

In our opinion, more attention should be paid to reading fiction and scientific literature for the general development and enrichment of professional oral speech. In order to actively develop oral speech, especially when it comes to a foreign language, it is important not only to learn words and grammar, but to practice speaking. To do this, it is important to find an interlocutor who knows Russian well and communicate with him only in the language being studied. Practice shows that working on pronunciation, intonation with the help of modern technologies, watching various TV shows and films, daily reading aloud helps to enrich oral speech.

It must be said that to interest modern youth in books, reading, and at the same time to use various forms of work with the book is not an easy task for the learner. The teacher of Russian language requires an individual approach to the learner, careful pedagogical preparation and selection of materials corresponding to the level of language proficiency. Based on many years of teaching experience, we offer the following materials based on the stories of L. Tolstoy, including multi-level tasks [2] (levels A1, A2 and B1) for club work or independent study:

<i>Stories for students who</i>	<i>Stories for students</i>	<i>Stories for students who</i>
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<i>Speak Russian at A1 level</i>	<i>Who speak Russian at A2 level</i>	<i>Speak Russian at B1 level</i>
Short stories, such as "The Monkey and the Pea", "The Learned Son", "The Mosquito and the Lion", etc.	Stories such as "The Old Grandfather and His Grandson", "The Bone", "Filippok", "The Girl and the Mushrooms", "The Fire", etc.	Stories-reasonings, such as "The Tsar and the Shirt", "The Shark", "The Jump", "The Kitten", etc.
Suggested target objectives for		
<p>trainer: teach learners to work with information correctly and perform phonetic exercises.</p> <p>learner: learn to work with text: correctly place stress marks, read expressively, develop attentiveness and memory, and also work on their own speech.</p>	<p>trainer: create conditions for independent work with text, teach how to collect information necessary to solve a problem, analyze it and draw conclusions.</p> <p>learner: learn how to work with text, reflect and express personal opinions, and also independently develop their own speech.</p>	<p>trainer: to develop critical thinking skills in the learner, allowing him to identify problems in the surrounding reality and effectively seek ways to solve them.</p> <p>learner: to be able to think critically, to see real life problems and strive to find rational ways to overcome them</p>

The proposed materials are aimed at the active development of oral speech. By retelling what has been read and analyzing the text, the student enriches his speech and enters into verbal interaction with others. At the same time, teachers and students themselves must consciously control their speech, get rid of filler words. Recording yourself on a dictaphone and analyzing speech errors is one of the ways to develop oral foreign speech. Frequent organization of discussions, debates, public speaking

are considered a necessity in enriching speech. In addition, it is necessary to teach a child a foreign language from an early age. It has been observed that in recent years in the country, parents have been specifically sending their children to Russian-language kindergartens and educational courses, paying special attention to their study of the language [3].

According to data, in 1992, there were 1,147 Russian-language schools in Uzbekistan. In 2000, there were already 813, and in 2015, even fewer - 739 Russian-language schools. As of 2020-2021, 903 schools were operating in Uzbekistan [3]. In large cities and villages, there are many courses and educational centers offering Russian language training for various age groups, which indicates significant interest in these services.

Conclusion

Thus, despite the processes of strengthening the role of the Uzbek language, Russian continues to be an important element in various aspects of life in the rapidly developing modern new Uzbekistan. The country's youth is actively interested in studying it, considering it as a tool for personal and professional growth. Russian as a non-native language remains an important tool for access to quality education, scientific and technical literature, as well as to the wider labor market, both within the country and abroad.

Knowledge of the Russian language expands the communicative capabilities of young professionals, contributes to their competitiveness and professional mobility. In addition, the Russian language continues to perform the function of interethnic communication, uniting the multinational society of Uzbekistan, which is especially important in the context of globalization and the development of international relations.

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